

Certainty Satiation Marketing for Disrupted Supply Chains

Daniel J. Finkenstadt, PhD
Naval Postgraduate School
Monterey CA

Robert Handfield, PhD
NC State University
Raleigh NC

Tojin T. Eapen, PhD
University of Missouri
Columbia MO

November 21, 2021

Abstract: Disrupted supply chains are not going to disappear anytime soon, and executives are wringing their hands on how to respond. We propose it's an opportune time for public and private supply chain executives to sit down with their marketing counterparts and have an honest discussion about what shortages and price increases lie ahead. Demand management is an important agility strategy that organizations should consider, applying our concept of certainty satiation marketing. This concept applies demand management to satiate consumer demand for resource availability certainty in volatile markets, in periods when irrational supply and demand behavior impact the global commons. COVID-19 has shown that markets will not behave rationally when product availability uncertainty and/or price stability is too high, and that irrational buying behaviors can have worldwide impacts.

Certainty Satiation Marketing for Disrupted Supply Chains

Abstract: Disrupted supply chains are not going to disappear anytime soon, and executives are wringing their hands on how to respond. We propose it's an opportune time for public and private supply chain executives to sit down with their marketing counterparts and have an honest discussion about what shortages and price increases lie ahead. Demand management is an important agility strategy that organizations should consider, applying our concept of certainty satiation marketing. This concept applies demand management to satiate consumer demand for resource availability certainty in volatile markets, in periods when irrational supply and demand behavior impact the global commons. COVID-19 has shown that markets will not behave rationally when product availability uncertainty and/or price stability is too high, and that irrational buying behaviors can have worldwide impacts.

Since the beginning of the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020 we have continued to see massive disruptions to our global supply chains, which has led to hoarding behavior in consumer and industrial markets. Initially it started with irrational hoarding of supplies like toilet paper, but also led to a “pile-on” effect) as disruptions to PPE supply prompted healthcare providers and distributors to place orders with anyone and everyone! As people realized that 90% of healthcare “medsurge” supplies were produced in Asia, COVID set off a mad scramble by all countries, states and organizations to obtain the necessary personal protective equipment (PPE) to stay open, many with varied levels of insight into available stock levels (Finkenstadt and Handfield, 2021). For instance, a large mask manufacturer we spoke with discussed how their monthly demand for N95 masks went from 2 million per month, to more than 1 billion for several months in a row! This level of massive surge in demand is difficult to comprehend, and even more difficult to manage. Such irrational demand can also lead to sharp drop-offs in future demand as stockpiles grow and uncertainty is assuaged. This can lead to companies having to reduce supply capability, impacting supply further downstream.

Researchers have found a plethora of likely contributing factors to this behavior such as social media and social cognitive biases, pandemic stress, fear of contagion, and particular personality traits (conscientiousness). (Labad et al., 2021). The current set of supply chain disruptions is being set off by a combination of COVID cases in manufacturing hubs around the world, labor shortages, lack of capital infrastructure investment, and surges in demand. This has led to a massive set of supply chain shortages, including a scarcity of microchips and massive container logjams in ports brought on by a combination of manufacturing losses during the pandemic shutdowns, and increased demand for consumer goods by a world forced to sit at home. In all of these situations there has been a disconnect in the ability for free

market price levels to **satiating demand**. How can we satiate downstream consumer demand and upstream suppliers being pressured to produce more than they are able to, in a world of point-and-click ordering combined with perceived scarcities? A new level of agility is required by firms to deal with the sudden shortfalls in supply to meet this demand. We propose that a new approach is needed. *Certainty satiation marketing involves demand moderation and creates a satiation effect that is an important approach for management the supply chain disruption realities we face today. It is focused primarily on managing the information and advice available to consumers so that they can reach satiation at the appropriate time, given environmental market conditions.*

Demand management has been handled in various ways. Natural price increases should manage demand, but we have seen that price increases can reach a point of hyperinflation. Rationing is another demand management strategy, but it has its downsides as well. Buyers and sellers develop strategies for consumption and production based on asymmetric information. Over time the market is supposed to reach a rational equilibrium. But major disruptions to markets for products that become global commons such as PPE, fuel, toilet paper etc. can lead to irrational buying and selling behaviors. Standard approaches used to inhibit irrational/unreasonable demand such as product rationing and tiered pricing are likely to lead to perception of scarcity, which in turn leaves customers unsatiated. This lack of satiation further drives up demand, aggravates the supply chain and creating a vicious demand satiation uncertainty loop (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Demand Satiation Uncertainty Loop

Unsatiated demand can lead to aggregate reactions such as stock-piling and black markets. Such demand inhibition strategies can also leave customers feeling cheated, disappointed or even angry, with potential for social and political fallout. In 2020 we saw everything from erratic toilet paper hoarding to consumers filling trash bags with fuel when domestic petroleum supplies were put at risk by weather and cyberattacks. In these cases, it would have been beneficial to manage demand with a concerted marketing strategy that sought to reduce asymmetric information and increase market certainty until things returned to normal.

Consumers continue to order and manufacturers continue to ship, but the global system is not prepared to logistically process a flow of irrational buying-selling behaviors brought on by the chaos of a pandemic. The supply chain is gummed up, and the cascading set of bottlenecks can only be understood in the context of “systems thinking”, that views the end to end supply chain as a series of nodes which must all flow seamlessly. Currently there are thousands of empty containers piling up in the port of Los Angeles and hundreds of container ships waiting days if not weeks to unload their cargo, further delaying deliveries and growing public sentiment that the supply chain cannot meet their demands. Rather than slow consumption many retailers are encouraging earlier and earlier buying for products that may not truly be in short supply, simply logistically pinned down. Increase buying won't help this as big box stores simply exacerbate the problem by chartering more ships to pile onto the heap. In our recent discussion with the White House Council of Economic Advisors, a group of academic advisors noted that the port of Los Angeles will likely remain a bottleneck for the foreseeable future, until such time as significant investments in digital technology can improve the integration of ocean-side containers with a hinterland strategy for optimizing trailers and rail cars into the port. Most of this is impacting imports from Asia, primarily China. As such, organizations who rely on Chinese imports should consider alternative approaches as demand will unlikely be met.

Satiation in economics can be defined as the point at which additional consumption beyond such a point would yield diminishing marginal utility relative to the cost to consume it. In the marketing literature, satiation is defined as “the process whereby consumers enjoy a stimulus less as they consume more of it” (Coombs and Avrunin 1977; Redden 2008; Sevilla and Reddin, 2014, p. 206), an outcome which most firms would prefer to avoid! In general, most marketers would favor conditions where consumers avoid reaching a point of satiation, and prefer continuous consumption to provide a stream of revenue and on-going profit maximization. Marketing research also suggests that people reach this satiation point as they consume additional quantities of an item or service and, once the satiation point is

reached, they move on to consume other types of products or services (Coombs and Avrunin, 1977; Herrnstein and Prelic, 1991). Research suggests that creating supply scarcities or perceptions of limited availability can prolong the point of consumer satiation and improve customer enjoyment over time (Sevilla and Reddin, 2014).

But how do we apply these concepts to the turbulent levels of supply chain disruption faced in our global economy today? Does it make sense to continue to try to reduce satiation rates, and continue to encourage consumers to consume as much as they want? Conversely, should firms continue to promote the scarcity of its products, sending a message of actual limited availability, and allow prices and thus revenues to continue to grow?

We suggest that these are not the optimal long-run paths for marketers, supply chain managers, firms, and governments to follow. Rather, both private and public sector organizations have a social responsibility to employ transparent and factual messaging, to create a new level of satiation for consumer certainty that may help to reduce strains on a global system of goods and services by increasing awareness of resource constraints. When information is sparse, trust may wane. A lack of trust in the system can lead to inefficient market behaviors by self-interested parties. This is consistent with the emerging view of a ‘commons’ during times of mass contingency and global healthcare disruption that became obvious during COVID-19. Our research suggests that the COVID-19 pandemic has created many new forms of supply chain commons for many public health goods and services, which should be based on transparency and equitability in supply chains to achieve a desired point of stabilization (Handfield et al., 2020; Finkenstadt et al., 2021). We suggest that the supply chain commons metaphor should be married with demand management concepts via certainty satiation. Certainty satiation marketing and supply chain commons planning can help consumers reach a point of satiation in resource certainty as a form of market demand management during a period of extreme supply chain disruption.

Demand management is a technique used in category management by supply chain and procurement professionals to prevent the buying of unneeded goods and services. The US government employs demand management as part of its category management program and considers it one of its five key recommendations for category management. The US government defines demand management as the practice of “analyzing what and how an agency is buying, with a specific focus on reducing the total cost of ownership” (p.9) by standardizing requirements, coordinating agencywide buying events, sharing demand strategies, and seeking volume-based (tiered) pricing (Weichart, 2019). The primary purpose of demand management in public procurement is to buy things “smarter” in an effort to increase value for

each dollar spent, reduce waste and increase public trust in the use of fiscal appropriations. The government has used these methods to improve sourcing in everything from milling machines for aircraft maintenance to working dogs for explosives and drug detection. These conservation mandates, which have been in use since World War II, can be equally applied to the private sector, and can be applied to mitigate the effect of supply chain disruptions for private sector markets. The government communicates demand management messages through policy and regulation, but such mandates cannot be as easily applied to free market consumers. All parties should consider alternative communication channels to inform consumers about the realities of available goods and services to reach a form of informed satiation; reducing the impacts of hoarding behaviors and/or logistical logjams. Currently we are seeing massive disruptions in almost every industrial and commodities sector. Beef and poultry prices are rising quickly, due to production and demand cycles; oil prices have reached \$80/bbl, and resin prices have also surged. Steel, aluminum, and copper are impacting the housing market, and the cost of electronics, appliances, and consumer packaged goods are all going up by 5% or more as a function of raw material shortages and disruptions. In recent conversation a CPO of a major CPG company shared how she was in the process of “educating” her Chief Marketing Officer on how raw material prices could not be made up through productivity, and that the only way to continue operating a profitable business was to pass on these price increases to consumers. Many companies have publicly announced they anticipate these shortages to continue well into 2022 and beyond. There is increasing evidence that companies need to educate consumers of the reality of what is happening in global supply chains, that is leading to longer lead times, increased pricing, and reduced product availability in retail and e-commerce channels. The irony of this point cannot be missed: we need to inform a broad consumer base that their commercial buying behaviors, resulting in a demand surge, are part of the reason for global supply chain disruptions!

In the past governments have tried to deal with these supply chain problems via social marketing. Public Service Announcements (PSAs) have been around in America since World War II as a form of social marketing. Social marketing is defined as “process that applies marketing principles and techniques to create, communicate and deliver value in order to influence target audience behaviors that benefit society (public health, safety, the environment, and communities) as well as the target audience” (Kotler, Lee and Rothschild, 2006 personal communication cited in Cheng, Kotler and Lee, 2009). Researchers have cited the use of social marketing for health promotion, injury prevention, environmental protection and community mobilization (Kotler and Lee, 2008). These marketing communications are intended to influence consumer behaviors to get them to 1) accept a new behavior such as buying electric vehicles, 2) reject a potential undesirable behavior such as taking up drug use, 3) modify current behaviors such as reducing water usage or 4) abandon an undesirable behavior such as driving without a

seatbelt. We have also seen the government use rationing as a means to control public demand for consumer goods. A downside is that this method has been found to increase the development of black markets. Black markets increase the risk of counterfeiting and we have seen that behavior occur in dangerous and unregulated ways for items like N95 masks, vaccines and vaccine cards during COVID19. So, we assume that we would prefer not to ration entire swaths of consumer goods and services. And this leads us back to social marketing.

We suggest that governments and firms consider this special form of marketing, *certainty satiation marketing*, as an alternative to traditional inhibiting forms of demand management such as social marketing, demand based pricing and rationing. We are NOT suggesting that we always tell customers to STOP consuming, as is done in social marketing to prevent environmental harm (i.e., reducing coal or petroleum fuel consumption). (Such behaviors have been adopted by the Chinese government around coal energy use, with deleterious effects on production levels). Instead, we are asking them to consider the impact on global commons (i.e. for the common good of humanity and the community) and utilize commons-focused communications about the market. Why is certainty satiation marketing different than traditional social marketing? The rationale driving certainty satiation marketing run counter to traditional marketing principles, and are not focused exclusively on modifying consumer behavior for a traditional social good.

The social benefit in this case is related to the need to ease constraints facing global supply chain operations. Supply chains are pivotal, as we have seen, to the flow of everything from food markets to defense markets, and shortages can create havoc in healthcare, air travel, transportation, and even a trip to the supermarket. Massive disruptions in the processing capabilities of supply chain systems are often triggered by irrational buying and selling behaviors; as these behaviors spread, the equivalent is a “bullwhip effect on steroids”, leading to chaos in global supply chain system performance. The imbalances currently facing supply chains is having major impacts on public health and welfare, but is even disrupting parts delivery for harvesting equipment for farmers, putting the 2021 fall harvest at risk when equipment cannot be maintained in a functioning state. But satiation marketing is also about clearly articulating the availability *and shortages* of goods to consumers which can reduce uncertainty, build trust, and improve cooperative market behaviors. The majority of consumers have the public good in mind, and the knowledge of scarcity will guide most consumers to make rational buying decisions within the spirit of that public good. This is not about stating how much or how little they should buy, but rather involves imploring consumers to only buy what they need, and not to hoard at the expense of others in their own communities.

This line of thinking may turn the marketer's job a bit on its head. Instead of focusing on delaying satiation by manipulating perceived scarcities for the purpose of continuous demand and revenues, the strategy involves increasing supply chain transparency and equitability for the purposes of reaching rational satiation levels commensurate with market realities. In a sense, creating alignment between demand and supply constraints is a means of informing consumer expectations, which will in most cases lead to measures of conservation.

It's worth emphasizing that conservation is not a bad thing, and is very much aligned with the current push on sustainability and reducing global carbon emissions. As noted previously, conservation measures during World War II led many private sector companies like GE and Ford to create a new engineering tool called Value Analysis and Value Engineering. The goal of VA/VE was straightforward: to simplify the design and manufacture of products, to achieve the equivalent or better functional outcome, at a lower or equal price. One of the most important tools in VA/VE was simplification and standardization, which involved using whatever material was in plentiful supply, and avoiding unique or difficult to order materials, including those that were being rationed by the US government like steel, cotton, etc. VA/VE proved to be an important option in the stable of tools in satiation marketing. Conservation was also applied during COVID in healthcare, when many hospitals began examining their clinical practices, and developed new recommendations for physicians, nurses and staff on how to reduce and reuse PPE, thus reducing the overall demand for masks, gowns, and gloves. An example was to reuse the gown one was wearing when visiting multiple patient rooms, and not to change into a new gown every time one entered a new room. Another example was to sterilize N95 masks using hydrochloric acid using approved FDA technologies. These policies made a huge dent in the volume of goods used by hospitals during a period when supply for PPE was stretched thin, and allowed many hospitals to scrape by without running out of PPE.

There is also risk that by not partaking in certainty satiation marketing, entities may choose to enact demand management strategies that seem helpful but are actually harmful. We have mentioned that rationing can lead to things like black markets. But it can also lead to opaque markets. For example, recently a non-profit PPE provider told us that they were unable to advertise domestically produced N95 masks on Google because Google had stated that the US government was asking them to not advertise N95s anymore due to supply shortages. However, the non-profit informed us that this supply shortage was only for traditional name brand products like 3M, not for newer domestic products. In effect Google was rationing advertising information. Google was unaware that there were a host of domestic respirator firms who were stood up using government funding in 2020 and were at risk for bankruptcy because they could not overcome the competition from cheap Asian products. Subsequently, these domestic

manufacturers couldn't get their advertising posted to take advantage of the market when those competitors were low on stock. If Google and the government were working to develop stronger certainty satiation marketing strategies, they could, instead, increase transparency into the types of products that were available for advertising (i.e. domestic respirators) and only advertise the traditional name brand (i.e. 3M) products once the available supply reached a predetermined level of stock that could meet demand. By rationing the information on available stock, Google had inadvertently contributed to the feeling of resource uncertainty, reduced the chances for onshore supply sustainability and left consumers in the dark.

As an alternative, we propose a softer approach to demand management which involves designing interventions to satiate (not inhibit) demand. As discussed above, irrational/unreasonable demand is driven by asymmetry of information, misaligned individual incentives,¹ and lack of trust. Thus, effective strategies can emerge from increased transparency of company *information*, aligning individual *incentives* to desired global outcomes, and encouraging broader customer *involvement* in the supply-chain process. There is a tradeoff here...high satiation requires higher customer (and company) effort. A company or agency might start with information based strategies, and then move to incentives, and then involvement. In the tables below we provide a list of potential interventions that can be used to satiate demand using information, incentives and involvement as drivers. Demand based pricing is not always a reliable control for demand when health is uncertain. Healthcare services have been historically inelastic (Ringel et al., 2002). During the first year of the pandemic healthcare products, such as PPE, became the same with prices soaring at times to 1,000%-2,000% for many items (Berklan, 2020). Rationing has been shown to lead to black markets for goods and services or strategic buying behaviors. During the early stages of the pandemic retailers were capping the amount of toilet paper each person could buy but customers were getting around this by having others who had already hoarded their stock buy for them or by making multiple store visits. And tiered pricing, where a consumer pays a higher per-unit price beyond a threshold quantity, is quickly rendered ineffective if consumers make multiple store-visits to purchase products at a lower price or when products are purchased by individuals hoping to profit from arbitrage. More importantly, these strategies drive a perception of scarcity, further fueling demand.

Satiation focused strategies leverage *information* to build trust and should be considered in the future. Simply providing further visibility into supply chains reduces uncertainty surrounding future availability of goods and services and can help to rationally balance demand. Of course, this assumes that suppliers and manufacturers have this visibility themselves. Social proof and quantity anchoring can be

¹ Individual's short terms incentives are misaligned with the broader welfare of society, as well as potentially the individual's own long-term interests.

used to give a clearer picture of others consumption rates, thereby influencing consumer's reference points for rational consumption in uncertain climates. Similar to social marketing, consequence extrapolation can be tailored to provide information about consumer demand and potential choices on the health and well-being of others. For example, COVID-19 vaccine booster shots are currently an ethical dilemma when half the world has not received their first shot. Yet human behavior in this uncertain time has caused many to seek their booster shots illicitly, impacting the global commons (Gutman, 2021). How might they behave if they knew the actual impact of jumping the line?

Incentive alignment tends to go hand-in-hand with supply chain visibility and has been shown to improve outcomes for all parties (Narayanan and Raman, 2004). Providing additional information lends itself to the ability to better align incentives. Suppliers could use methods that align price savings features of a product to its actual usage versus simply a promotional period of time. If suppliers were to provide promotional coupons on products that can only be accessed as they are consumed it could incentivize less near-term hoarding in favor of long-term cost-savings. At the same time suppliers and retailers can look to supply-based promotions as a way of moving excess stock of substitution products. For example, in the case of N95 masks, producers could offer better pricing for domestic product during a time when traditional, cheaper suppliers are short of supply, and advertising platforms like Google can help highlight them during such a period and thus increase the overall benefit to the greater commons supply chain and consumer. In a similar manner time-shifted promotions can have similar effects by providing discounts into a future period when normal consumption would be assumed to have taken place. Price promotion need not be the only mechanism shifted to rebalance demand.

Buy-now deliver later (BNDL) and subscription warranties provides a mechanism for reducing future availability uncertainty by allowing consumers to preorder items and simply wait on them to arrive at a called upon date in terms of BNDL or a specified delivery schedule in terms of subscription warranties. This creates a means of delaying delivery until a normal, more rational, consumption period expires. However, both of these methods require a great degree of trust on the part of the consumer that firms and governments can support through strong enforcement governance and supply chain transparency.

Building trust may not occur in the chaos of a pandemic or other mass calamity without getting the consumers, firms and governments *involved* in collaborative activities that build on information transparency and incentive-alignment. Google Trends shows that from Oct 2019 to Nov 2021 searches for supply chain "shortage", "crisis", and "management" are up 900%, 500% and 250% respectively. The public is aware there is a problem, and they are more curious than ever in recent history. It is an exceptionally opportune time to use trust-building engagements with the public to discuss efficient, resilient, and ethical supply chain management and consumer demand behavior during times of global

crises. This can be used to encourage actions as simple as group purchasing with capped quantities at lower prices, to engaging in crowdsourcing solutions to supply and demand issues plaguing these new market commons in a post-pandemic world. Certainty satiation marketing can be addressed through means such as webinars, published open-source research and open discussions on social audio platforms like Clubhouse© for a start.

TRADITIONAL DM	SATIATION-FOCUSED DM INTERVENTIONS		
Inhibition	Information	Incentives	Involvement
Demand based pricing	Supply chain visibility	Time-shifted promotions	Trust-building
Product rationing	Consequence extrapolation	Consumption-linked pricing	Group purchases
Tiered pricing	Quantity anchoring	Subscription warranties	Conservation
<i>Low Customer Effort</i> <i>Unsatiated</i>	<i>Low Customer Effort</i> <i>Low Satiation</i>	<i>Moderate Customer Effort</i> <i>Moderate Satiation</i>	<i>High Customer Effort</i> <i>High Satiation</i>

Table 1: Comparison of Example Demand Management (DM) Strategies

DM Driver	Strategy	Summary and Limitations
INHIBITION	Demand based pricing	Customer pay a higher price when aggregate demand goes up. This is the standard economic response to increased demand and is associated by the customer with inflation.
	Product rationing	Each customer or household is allowed to purchase only a fixed quantity. Customers are sometimes required to show identification.
	Tiered pricing	The consumer pays regular price for a threshold number of units. Purchase beyond this quantity is charged a higher price. Theoretically, there is no limit on purchase quantity.
INFORMATION	Supply chain visibility	Consumers are made aware of specific information about the supply chain to assuage concerns regarding availability.
	Social proof and Quantity Anchoring	Consumers are shown information relating to suggested quantity that can potentially satiates demand. For example, a message next to the product might read, “An average person in the US consumes an equivalent two units of the product per week.”
	Consequence Extrapolation	People are provided information about needs of other users or provided with dynamic information on how their potential choice (if extrapolated) can impact the global commons or other individual consumers.

INCENTIVES	Consumption-linked pricing/promotion	Promotions or coupons only visible to customers once the product is opened or consumed. For example, a coupon that is printed on one of the tissues roll cores for a discount. ²
	Supply-based promotions	Promotion of products that are excess in supply.
	Time-shifted promotions	Promotions that are redeemable only at future date. Time shifted promotions are designed to even the customer demand. Let's say each unit of product is given a single coupon for 10% discount. However, the coupon is only redeemable after 1 month from the purchase of the original product. ³
	Buy-now deliver later (BNDL)	Products can be ordered today for a future delivery at current price. Consumers are guaranteed of obtaining product at today's price and save on storage space. ⁴
	Subscription warranties	Consumers can buy vouchers for future delivery of products which if unfulfilled will result in penalty payout by the company. ⁵
INVOLVEMENT	Trust-building	Consumer groups are encouraged to participate in discussions about supply chain to build trust within communities.
	Group purchases	Group discounts where groups are allowed to buy products for a lower price with limitations on overall items purchased by a group
	Conservation and Education Campaigns	Customers are involved in supply chain conservation and management efforts. For example, crowdsourcing contests could be used to encourage customer participation in the global supply chain. Education campaigns on supply chain conditions, demand management, and risks to the global commons provided via webinar, open-source literature and social media and audio platforms.

Table 2: Summary of Example Demand Management (DM) Strategies

We can't solve all of the supply chain woes of the past two years with these ideas. But we can suggest exploration into a new form of research, public policy, and business practice focusing on

² This approach partly solves the dilemma that irrational demand is both a good problem and a bad problem to have. The supplier needs to even demand.

³ For example, for every toilet roll box purchased, the customer is given a discount coupon with a future redemption date that is 2-3 months away from current purchase date. The redemption date may be randomly staggered to further even future demand.

⁴ This strategy responds to consumers' concern about future increase in prices.

⁵ This strategy responds to consumers' concern about future availability of product.

illuminating supply chain conditions for the purposes of reaching a rationale point of consumer demand during global disruptions. We simply implore the world to look for greater information symmetry, trust, incentive-alignment, and stakeholder collaboration in an effort to help curb moments of unsatiated, irrational, and collectively harmful demand. This is a new form of marketing focused primarily on managing the information and advice available to consumers so that they can reach satiation at the appropriate time, given environmental market conditions. Certainty satiation marketing needs further consideration to help us manage the flow of global goods and services. Private sector companies should work with their sales and marketing teams, to promote the right commons-based communications to consumers about allocation levels, and what to expect given the shortages that are imminent at Christmas time. Public sector companies need to be straightforward in their communications with their agencies on the level of backorders, long lead times, price increases, and availability of supply for critical goods. Farm equipment, construction, and automobile manufacturers need to work with their dealer network to help them understand how to re-use or re-manufacture difficult to purchase parts to support their on-going maintenance issues. We need to eliminate the demand satiation uncertainty loop that has haunted us these past two years and get our supply chains back on track. We believe that certainty satiation marketing can help and should become a standard strategy for firms and agencies in the post-pandemic world.

References:

1. Andersen, E. Satiation in an evolutionary model of structural economic dynamics. *Journal of Evolutionary Economics* 11, 143–164 (2001). <https://doi.org/10.1007/PL00003852>
2. Berkman, J.M. (2020). Analysis: PPE costs increase over 1,000% during COVID-19 crisis Retrieved 8 November 2021 from: <https://www.mcknights.com/news/analysis-ppe-costs-increase-over-1000-during-covid-19-crisis/>
3. Cheng, H., Kotler, P. and Lee, N.R. (2009) *Social Marketing for Public Health*, Chapter 1. pp. 1-30
4. Coombs, Clyde H. and George S. Avrunin (1977), “Single-Peaked Functions and the Theory of Preference,” *Psychological Review*, 84 (2), 216–30.
5. Finkenstadt, D.J. and Handfield R. (2021). *Journal of Purchasing & Supply Management* 27 (2021). Blurry vision: Supply chain visibility for personal protective equipment during COVID-19. *Journal of Purchasing and Supply Management*, 27(3).
6. Gutman R. (2021). Booster Bandits Are Walking a Fine Line: Getting an illicit third shot has gone mainstream, but it’s still a real ethical dilemma. *The Atlantic*. Retrieved 8 November 2021 from: <https://www.theatlantic.com/health/archive/2021/09/booster-bandits-ethics/620048/>
7. Handfield R, Finkenstadt DJ, Schneller ES, Godfrey AB, Guinto P. A Commons for a Supply Chain in the Post-COVID-19 Era: The Case for a Reformed Strategic National Stockpile. *Milbank Quarterly*. 2020;98(4):1058-1090. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1468-0009.12485>
8. Herrnstein, Richard J. and Drazen Prelec (1991), “Melioration: A Theory of Distributed Choice,” *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 5 (3), 137–56.
9. Kotler, P. and Lee, N.R. (2008). *Social marketing: Influencing behaviors for good* (3rd ed.) Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications
10. Labad, J., González-Rodríguez, A., Cobo, J., Puntí, J., & Farré, J. M. (2021). A systematic review and realist synthesis on toilet paper hoarding: COVID or not COVID, that is the question. *PeerJ*, 9, e10771. <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.10771>
11. Narayanan V.G. and Raman, A. (2004). Aligning Incentives in Supply Chains. *Harvard Business Review*. <https://hbr.org/2004/11/aligning-incentives-in-supply-chains>
12. Sevilla J, Redden JP. Limited Availability Reduces the Rate of Satiation. *Journal of Marketing Research*. 2014;51(2):205-217. doi:10.1509/jmr.12.0090
13. Redden, Joseph P. (2008), “Reducing Satiation: The Role of Categorization Level,” *Journal of Consumer Research*, 34 (5), 624–34.
14. Weichart, M.M. (2019). “Category Management: Making Smarter Use of Common Contract Solutions and Practices” Office of Management and Budget Government Memorandum No. M-19-13

12. Ringel, Jeanne S., Susan D. Hosek, Ben A. Vollaard, and Sergej Mahnovski, *The Elasticity of Demand for Health Care: A Review of the Literature and Its Application to the Military Health System*, Santa Monica, Calif.: RAND Corporation, MR-1355-OSD, 2002. As of November 01, 2021: https://www.rand.org/pubs/monograph_reports/MR1355.html

15.